

PROCESSING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBON NANOTUBE / POLYLACTIC ACID NANOCOMPOSITE FILMS

Erin M. Sullivan¹, Parvin Karimineghlani², Francesca Gencarella³, Renee Puvvada¹, Ben Wang^{1,4},
Rosario Gerhardt¹, Mohammad Naraghi⁵, and Kyriaki Kalaitzidou^{1,3}

¹School of Materials Science and Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology
771 Ferst Drive, Atlanta, Georgia, 30332, U.S.A.

Email: erin.sullivan@gatech.edu, web page: <http://www.mse.gatech.edu>

²Department of Materials Science & Engineering, Texas A&M University
3003 TAMU, College Station, Texas, 77843, U.S.A.

Email: parvin.karimi2007@gmail.com, web page: <http://engineering.tamu.edu/materials>

³G.W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology
801 Ferst Drive, Atlanta, Georgia, 30332, U.S.A.

Email: kyriaki.kalaitzidou@me.gatech.edu, web page: <http://www.me.gatech.edu>

⁴Georgia Tech Manufacturing Institute, Georgia Institute of Technology
813 Ferst Drive, Atlanta, Georgia, 30332, U.S.A.

Email : ben.wang@gatech.edu, web page: <http://www.manufacturing.gatech.edu>

⁵Department of Aerospace Engineering, Texas A&M University
3141 TAMU, College Station, Texas, 77843, U.S.A.

Email : naraghi@tamu.edu, web page: <http://engineering.tamu.edu/aerospace>

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotube (CNT) / polylactic acid (PLA) composite films were fabricated via two methods: 1) melt compounding and melt fiber spinning followed by compression molding (MC-CM) and 2) solution compounding and electrospinning followed by compression molding (E-CM). The effect of the two processing methods on the morphology, crystallization behaviour, thermo-mechanical behaviour, and electrical response of the fibers and films was examined. With CNT's superior conductivity, PLA's conductivity can be enhanced, making it a biodegradable alternative to current conductive films made of petroleum based polymers for static dissipation applications. Melt spun and electrospun fiber morphology was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The crystallinity and crystal structure was investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). Thermo-mechanical properties of the films was examined using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). Finally, electrical properties were investigated using impedance spectroscopy (IS). The melt spun fibers had a larger average fiber diameter compared to the electrospun fibers which may influence the distribution and dispersion of the CNT throughout the matrix. However, the crystallization behaviour of the films were comparable both in terms of crystallinity content (%) and average lamella thickness. The storage modulus of the films increased with the addition of CNT into the PLA matrix due to the CNT hindering polymer chain mobility. Finally, the films became conductive at low CNT concentrations. The films were percolated at less than 1wt% CNT for the E-CM films and less than 3wt% CNT for the MC-CM films.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polylactic acid (PLA) is a biodegradable, aliphatic thermoplastic polyester derived from cornstarch or sugarcane [1]. Its properties are comparable to petroleum based counterparts, such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polystyrene (PS) [1, 2]. Furthermore, the increase in production capability over

recent years has increased its viability to replace these comparable petroleum based plastics in a wide range of applications from biomedical devices and food packaging to electronics and electronics packaging [3, 4]. Despite desirable mechanical properties, the use of PLA in electronics applications is limited without enhancing and tailoring static dissipation capabilities through the addition of fillers, like carbon nanotubes (CNT). Since their observation in 1991 [5], CNT have attracted interest for their superior mechanical performance, low density, and conductive properties [6, 7]. CNT are a tubular configuration of graphite sheets. The high aspect ratio of the cylindrical structure allows for a virtually one dimensional electronic structure with very little scattering [8]. By incorporating CNT into the PLA matrix, the electrical properties of the resultant composite can be significantly enhanced.

This study aims to incorporate CNT into a PLA matrix via two processing methods: 1) melt compounding followed by melt fiber spinning and compression molding and 2) solution compounding followed by electrospinning and compression molding. The effect of compounding method on composite film crystallization behaviour, thermo-mechanical properties, and electrical response is investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Semicrystalline PLA (PLA 3051D) in pellet form was purchased from Nature Works LLC and used as the matrix material. The PLA has a flow index of 10-30 g/10 min, ASTM D1238, a specific gravity of 1.24, and an average molecular weight of 160 kg/mol. CNT (multi-walled, >95wt% purity) purchased from Cheap Tubes Inc. with an average length of 10-20 μm and an average outer diameter between 30-50 nm were used as the reinforcement. Chloroform and dimethylformamide (DMF) were used as the solvents for electrospinning.

2.2 Processing

The composite films were fabricated using two different compounding methods: melt compounding followed by melt fiber spinning and compression molding or solution compounding followed by electrospinning and compression molding. For the melt compounded / compression molded (MC-CM) films, the CNT were incorporated into the matrix by melt blending using a vertical co-rotating twin screw microextruder (DSM 15cc Compounder) at an operating temperature of 190°C and a screw speed of 150 RPM. The compound is then extruded out of a 0.8 mm orifice at a 15 RPM pull-out rate and melt spun into fibers of $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ diameter (draw ratio of ~ 8). Melt fiber spinning prior to compression molding allows for better control over agglomeration size and orientation/distribution of the nanofiller. Melt spun composite fibers were then compression molded into films $\sim 110 \mu\text{m}$ thick using a manual four-column 12 ton Carver hydraulic press (model 4122). The fibers are first softened for ~ 5 minutes at 180°C before a pressure of ~ 1 MPa is applied for ~ 5 minutes. Plastic deformation is minimized by allowing the films to cool below the glass transition temperature ($\sim 50^\circ\text{C}$) via ambient air cooling prior to removal from the mold.

The second processing method utilized solution compounding followed by electrospinning and compression molding (E-CM). A 10 wt% solution of PLA in chloroform was first prepared by stirring with low heat until the PLA pellets dissolved. The appropriate amount of CNT to produce a 1wt% CNT/PLA composite fiber was added to DMF and sonicated for 3 hours to homogenize. The CNT/DMF suspension was added to the PLA/chloroform solution and stirred for 1 hour. The electrospinning was performed under ambient conditions using a rotating collector and applied voltage of 16 kV. The distance between the syringe tip and the collector was 15 cm and the feeding rate of the solution was 100 $\mu\text{L/h}$. The resultant electrospun composite fibers of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter were compression molded under identical conditions to the melt spun fibers, as described above. Due to the high viscosity of the CNT/PLA/chloroform/DMF solution, the amount of CNT in the electrospun fibers was limited to 1wt%.

2.3 Characterization

Morphology of the fibers is examined using a Phenom World G2 Pro scanning electron microscope (SEM) at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. In order to eliminate charging, samples were first coated with gold using a Cressington Sputter Coater 108 (model 6002) at ~0.08 mbar and ~30 mA and a 30 second deposition time.

Crystallization behaviour and thermal transitions are examined using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), TA Instruments DSC Q2000. 5-7 mg samples are prepared in standard Tzero aluminum pans, equilibrated at 20°C, and held isothermal for 5 minutes. The samples are heated to 175°C at a rate of 5°C/min and then cooled down to 20°C at a rate of 5°C/min. To preserve thermal history, a result of processing conditions, the initial heating cycle is considered for analysis. The crystal structure of the composites is examined using X-ray diffraction (XRD). XRD measurements are performed using an X'Pert Pro Alpha 1 (PANalytical, Almelo, Netherlands) diffractometer. (Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.541 \text{ \AA}$) The diffraction patterns are collected from a 2θ angle of 8° to 40° with a step size of ~0.02. (The diffractometer is operated at 45 kV and 40 mA).

Thermo-mechanical properties are examined using a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA), TA Instruments DMA Q800. Rectangular specimens ~110 μm thick and ~2 mm wide with a gauge length of ~10 mm were tested in tensile mode. The samples were heated from 35°C to 100°C at a rate of 3°C/min. The tests were conducted with oscillation amplitude of 12 μm and a constant frequency of 1 Hz.

The electrical response of the films is examined using impedance spectroscopy (IS). A Solartron 1260 Impedance/Gain Phase Analyzer along with a 1296 Dielectric Interface is used to measure in the 0.1 Hz – 10 MHz frequency range at 500 mV applied voltage.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Fiber Morphology

Melt fiber spinning and electrospinning resulted in a difference in fiber diameter and morphology. This fiber morphology can be seen in Figure 1. The melt spun PLA fibers have a much larger average fiber diameter of ~100 μm , while the electrospun neat PLA fibers have an average diameter on the order of 10 μm . Furthermore, the electrospun neat PLA fibers, seen in Figure 1c, have significant porosity. The porosity may be attributed to the rapid evaporation of solvent during the electrospinning process.

Figure 1: Representative SEM of a) melt spun neat PLA fibers, b) electrospun neat PLA fibers, and c) high magnification image of electrospun neat PLA fibers

As shown in Figure 2, after the CNT is incorporated, the diameter of the electrospun fibers decreases to less than 1 μm and agglomerations can be seen indicated by the arrow in Figure 2b. Neither the

diameter of the melt spun fibers or the morphology of the melt spun fibers changes with the addition of CNT. The difference in fiber diameter will influence the distribution and dispersion of the CNT in the film. The smaller fiber diameter of the electrospun fibers may allow for a more homogeneous distribution and dispersion of nanofiller throughout the matrix compared to the MC-CM films.

Figure 2: Representative SEM of a) melt spun 1wt% CNT fiber and b) electrospun 1wt% CNT fibers. Arrow indicates agglomeration

3.2 Crystallization Characteristics

The thermal and crystallization behaviour of the films was examined using initial heating thermograms. The glass transition temperature (T_g) and percent crystallinity (χ) is shown in Table 1. The percent crystallinity is calculated using the following equation:

$$\chi = \frac{\Delta H_m + \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_m^\circ(1 - wt\%/100)} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where χ is the percent crystallinity, ΔH_m is the melting enthalpy of the sample, $\Delta H_c (< 0)$ is the cold crystallization enthalpy of the sample, ΔH_m° is the melting enthalpy of 100% crystalline PLA, and is 93 J/g [9, 10], and $wt\%$ is the CNT weight percent in the composite.

	χ (%)		T_g (°C)	
	MC-CM	E-CM	MC-CM	E-CM
0wt% CNT	16.8 ± 6.0	31.2 ± 2.7	61.2 ± 0.2	59.5 ± 0.5
1wt% CNT	37.9 ± 0.8	36.7 ± 0.5	60.5 ± 0.3	60.1 ± 0.2
2wt% CNT	37.8 ± 0.7	--	60.0 ± 0.3	--
3wt% CNT	35.5 ± 1.0	--	60.6 ± 0.2	--

Table 1: Percent crystallinity (χ) and glass transition temperature (T_g) as a function of processing and CNT content

As seen in Table 1, the T_g of both the MC-CM and E-CM films remained constant at ~60°C even with the addition of CNT. The 0wt% CNT MC-CM displayed much more amorphous behaviour and upon addition of CNT, the χ increased significantly. This indicates that the CNT is acting as a nucleating agent, promoting crystallization of the PLA matrix. However, the high crystallinity of the 0wt% CNT E-CM film and the relatively small increase in crystallinity with the addition of CNT suggests that the increase in crystallinity seen in the MC-CM films has less to do with the presence of CNT and could be due to the differences in processes between the MC-CM and E-CM films. Their could be remnant solvent or other contaminants in the E-CM films that are altering the crystallization behaviour.

The percent crystallinity is only one aspect of the crystallization behaviour. Diffraction patterns were

examined in order to investigate the crystal structure. PLA has three primary crystal phases: α , β , and γ and a secondary, less stable, disordered α' phase produced at low crystallization temperatures and can be converted to α phase upon heating [11]. Both MC-CM and E-CM films displayed sharp, α phase crystal diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 15.0^\circ$, 16.7° , 19.1° , and 22.4° corresponding to characteristic crystallographic planes of (010) [12], (200+110) [13], (203) [12], and (121) [12], respectively. The sharp diffraction peaks correlate to the high crystallinity seen in Table 1 while the presence of only one primary α crystal phase indicates that there is no polymorphism in either MC-CM or E-CM films. There is no visible characteristic CNT diffraction peak in either films due to PLA crystal structure dominating the behaviour.

The average lamella thickness for the two primary diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 16.7^\circ$ and 19.1° was calculated using the Scherrer equation below:

$$L = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (2)$$

where L is the apparent crystalline lamella thickness, K is a dimensionless shape factor (0.9 was used as an approximate for the spherulite structure [14]), λ is the radiation wavelength, B is the full width at half maximum value of the diffraction peak, and θ is the Bragg angle. The average lamella thickness is shown in Table 2. There is not a statistically significant difference between the MC-CM and E-CM films lamella thickness. Because the average lamella thickness is equivalent, the higher percent crystallinity for the 0wt% E-CM film compared to the 0wt% MC-CM film is attributed to the presence of more spherulites, not thicker spherulites.

	16.7° (nm)		19.1° (nm)	
	MC-CM	E-CM	MC-CM	E-CM
0wt% CNT	24.5 ± 2.2	26.3 ± 0.4	13.1 ± 0.1	15.4 ± 0.7
1wt% CNT	25.1 ± 0.8	26.8 ± 0.9	16.8 ± 0.7	17.0 ± 0.9
2wt% CNT	28.2 ± 0.5	--	17.3 ± 1.8	--
3wt% CNT	25.1 ± 0.8	--	16.3 ± 0.2	--

Table 2: Average lamella thickness for $2\theta = 16.7^\circ$ and 19.1° diffraction peaks

3.3 Thermo-mechanical Properties

The thermo-mechanical properties of the films were examined and a representative run for each of the films can be seen in Figure 3. The storage modulus (E'), seen in Figure 3a, is representative of the stiffness of the films and decreases with increased temperature and molecular mobility [15, 16]. The E' reported at 35°C is significantly lower for the 0wt% MC-CM film compared to the 0wt% E-CM film. The E' is ~ 1900 MPa and ~ 2600 MPa, respectively. This increase in E' may be due to the higher crystallinity of the 0wt% E-CM film compared to the 0wt% MC-CM film. An increase in E' is a result of hindered polymer chain mobility [16, 17] and of the fact that the ordered crystalline lamella will have a lower mobility than the amorphous polymer chains at equivalent temperature [18].

3.4 Electrical Properties

In-plane impedance measurements were performed as a function of frequency. The low frequency impedance magnitude ($|Z^*|$) is proportional to resistance and because all films measured have comparable dimensions, $|Z^*|$ is also proportional to resistivity. Both the 1wt% E-CM film and the 3wt% MC-CM films display conductive behaviour, with a low frequency $|Z^*|$ on the order of $10^6 \Omega$. The neat PLA films are highly insulating with a low frequency $|Z^*|$ on the order of $10^{12} \Omega$. The MC-CM films percolate below 3wt% CNT, while the E-CM films percolate below 1wt% CNT. Further investigation is needed to better isolate and identify the percolation threshold for the two sets of films. The variance in fiber diameter may influence the dispersion and distribution, which would have a

direct correlation to the electrical response and percolation threshold.

Figure 3: Representative a) storage modulus and b) loss modulus plots as a function of processing and CNT content

4 CONCLUSIONS

CNT/PLA films were fabricated via two processing methods: 1) melt compounding and melt fiber spinning followed by compression molding and 2) solution compounding and electrospinning followed by compression molding. The fiber morphology and average diameter was examined and compared for the two processing methods. The electrospun fibers had a significantly smaller average fiber compared to the melt spun fibers. The MC-CM and E-CM films had comparable percent crystallinity and lamella thickness, with the exception of the 0wt% E-CM film displaying a much higher percent crystallinity compared to the 0wt% MC-CM film. Both sets of films exhibited an increase in stiffness with the addition of CNT; however, the 0wt% E-CM film had a much larger E' compared to the 0wt% MC-CM film. This may be due to the presence of contaminants in the 0wt% E-CM film. Both the MC-CM and E-CM films displayed conductive behaviour at low concentrations of CNT. The E-CM films at 1wt% CNT and the MC-CM films at 3wt%. In conclusion, processing method can alter the overall composite properties by changing distribution and dispersion of the nanofiller and crystallization behaviour of the polymer matrix.

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